

AUDITORY CUES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON BRAND SUCCESS IN QUICK-SERVICE RESTAURANTS IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: This study sought to understand the nexus between auditory perception and brand performance in the context of quick-service restaurants in Rivers State. The study adopted a cross sectional research design with a correlational investigation type. The population for this study comprised the 15 registered quick-service restaurants operating in Rivers State, which are also enlisted in the Nigerian Directories and Search Engine. The study adopted the Census method and administered four (4) copies of questionnaire to management staff from each of the 15 firms, making it a total of 60 respondents for the study. These managers included Operations Managers, Customer Service Managers, Marketing Managers and Supervisors of quick service restaurants in Rivers State. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used in testing the various hypotheses with the help of the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences Version 23.0. The findings revealed existence of significant nexus between auditory perception and brand performance of quick-service restaurants in Rivers State. Based on the findings, the study concluded that auditory perception has significant nexus with brand performance of quick service restaurants in Rivers State. The study recommended that managers of quick service restaurants should carefully curate their auditory landscapes to enable an atmosphere that appeals to their target audience and align their services with their brand performance; they should also consider the strategic role of auditory perception in their quest to understand consumer behaviour, this would boost brand loyalty as well as improve overall performance.

Key Words: Auditory Perception, Brand Performance, Brand Satisfaction, Brand Trust, Brand Loyalty.

Introduction

Human actions are based on the experiences gained through our sense. The human senses are so powerful that it can tap into an individual's exact emotions. By trying to understand the exact sense of the consumer and the effect it may have on the product, helps the manufacturer to create their brands more uniquely with a personal touch (Dijrovik 2008). Sensory marketing is a strategy used to enhance the relationship between consumer and the brand. As described by Hulten (2009) there are 5 sensors and sensory expressions. They are identified as Visual (Sight), Atmospheric (Smell), Tactile (Touch), Gustative (Taste) and Auditory (Hearing). By integrating the five

senses with multisensory experiences and culturally competent strategies, brands can create longterm relationships with customers, bringing them closer to their brands.

The noise, music, and sounds made while eating constitute sensory stimuli that can increase appetite and consumers’ appraisal of dishes (Spence & Shankar, 2010). Sensory perception is based on the concept that we are most likely to form, memorise, and discover the mind when all five senses are involved. By going outside the traditional marketing media of sight and sound, brands can establish a stronger and longer-lasting emotional connection with consumers. Sensory perception is used in different aspects: visual, auditory, olfactory, gustative, and tactile marketin (Krupka, 2023). Sensory perception appeals to all the senses in relation to the brand. It uses the senses to relate with customers at an emotional level. Several scholars have described Sensory perception as a means to appeal to consumers about a brands.

Quick-service restaurants display sounds like a music, or a piece of art aimed at captivating customers. Auditory factors influence people’s decision expcially when they are to choose between two similar restaurants. Scholars in the field of marketing have recognized the importance of auditory perception in boosting brand performance of quick-service restaurants (Krupka, 2023). For instance, Clemes et al. (2013) observed that music, sounds and other facilities, can influence customer perceptions. It appears that Rivers State quick-service resturants are bereft of the significance and role of auditory perception in the achievement of brand performance. Existing literature shows that there is paucity of documented studies on theoretical and empirical relationship between these concepts in the context of quick-service resturants in Rivers State. Besides, the documented studies have reported conflicting results; while some studies (such as Fong, Lei, Chow & Lam, 2023; Kuo, Liu, Wang & Chen, 2023; Huang & Labroo, 2020; Rodriguez, Reyes & Carvalho, 2023; Errajaa, Legohérel, Daucé & Bilgihan, 2021; Kuczamer-Kłopotowska, 2017; Randhir, Latasha, Tooraiven & Monishan, 2016) reported divergent links between the concepts. Motivated by the dearth of theoretical and empirical studies and a couple empirical inconsistencies, this study is poised to explore the nexus between auditory perception and brand performance in the context of quick-service resturants in Rivers State.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the nexus between auditory perception and brand performance of quick-service restaurants in Rivers State

Sources: Dissabandara and Dissanayake (2019); Sharma (2019).

Literature Review

The Theory of Planned Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) is a widely recognised psychological framework that seeks to explain the processes underlying human behaviour. Developed by Icek Ajzen in the late 20th century, this theory builds upon the earlier Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by incorporating additional components to account for factors influencing behaviour beyond individual volition. In his comprehensive review, Ajzen (1991) outlined how TPB can be used to predict various behaviours, ranging from health-related actions to consumer choices, thus establishing it as a versatile tool in social psychology. Perceived behavioural control refers to an individual's perception of their ability to perform a behaviour. This assumption recognises that external factors and personal confidence can influence intentions. Ajzen (1991) emphasises that even if individuals have favourable attitudes and perceive social approval, their actual control over behaviour can impact their intentions. One of the core components of TPB is the role of attitudes in shaping intentions. Sensory marketing strategies that create positive experiences—such as appealing visuals, pleasant scents, and engaging sounds—can enhance consumer attitudes toward a brand. When consumers have favourable experiences, their positive evaluations contribute to stronger intentions to purchase (Ajzen, 1991). For example, a store that uses inviting sounds can create a positive emotional response, leading consumers to associate the brand with enjoyable experiences. The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) helps us understand how sensory marketing strategies can change how people act and how well a brand does in this study. By examining the interplay between consumers' attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioural controls, and intentions, TPB helps explain how sensory experiences impact purchasing decisions and overall brand effectiveness.

Concept of Auditory Perception

Audition is a crucial component of sensory marketing, significantly influencing consumers' perceptions and behaviours. The auditory system processes sound in a way that affects emotional and cognitive responses, making it an effective tool for marketers seeking to create memorable brand experiences (Krishna, 2012). Sound, whether it is music, ambient noise, or spoken language, can evoke emotions, create associations, and reinforce brand identity. This dimension of sensory marketing works by influencing consumers' moods, altering their perceptions of products and services, and shaping their overall experience (Ballantine, Jack, & Parsons, 2010). Marketers strategically employ auditory cues to complement other sensory stimuli, ensuring a comprehensive and engaging consumer interaction. Music is one of the most commonly used auditory elements in marketing due to its ability to shape consumer experiences across various contexts. Brand Performance Brand performance refers to the interrelated measurement of brand success in the marketplace. Brand performance refers to the interconnected measurement of brand success in the marketplace. O'Cass and Ngo (2007) defined brand performance as the comparative measurement of the success of the brand in the marketplace. This is because brand performance can also be perceived as the brand succeeding the firm's reputable aspirations for them in the marketplace. Thus, the study adopts brand satisfaction, brand trust, and brand loyalty as measures of brand performance. Brand Satisfaction: According to such a paradigm, brand satisfaction is defined as a post-purchase psychological status representing the evaluation of a brand's usage experience. It depends, therefore, on the extent as well as on the direction of the discrepancy between the perceived performance and the standard of comparison. Brand Trust: Brand trust is the prevailing belief and assurance a particular customer may have in a brand. Brand trust measures the different customers' confidence in the company. It is a clear reflection of how the brand delivers on its

promises and stays true to the overall values it reflects (Schlecht, 2003). **Brand Loyalty:** Brand loyalty consists of a high degree of bonding between a customer and a brand. Loyal customers are unwilling to switch brands and prefer to stick with one that they feel comfortable and satisfied with (Rosenbaum-Elliott et al., 2011). Customers who are loyal towards a brand are also less price sensitive and open to paying a higher price for a specific brand compared to other alternatives, since consumers may perceive a unique value in the brand. Quick-service restaurants serve as an alternative source of food supplies to home-cooked meals for workers and travellers on the move. Globally, there is an increasing demand for food away from home, which has given impetus to quick service restaurants (Olorunfunmi & Kayii, 2019; Agu, Kalu & Agaeze, 2017). Today, quick service restaurants are everywhere within cities and towns. The busy and hectic lifestyle in the modern world has resulted in an increasing number of people patronising fast food and restaurants during working hours, as it is considered a time-saving product (Ojinnaka, 2011; Harcourt, Kayii & Ikegwuru, 2020). Nigeria is at the verge of the restaurant revolution, and the eating habits of Nigerians are changing; the style of cooking and the ingredients used increased the popularity of Nigerian food industries (Petzer & Mackay, 2014). Traditionally, people in Rivers State prefer their own cuisine as compared to fast food/restaurants. As a result, most people cook and eat at home rather than dine at the restaurants. However, in recent times, there are some changes in consumer trends that have increased the popularity of eating outside (Woo-Hyuk, Sang-Ho & Kyung-Sook, 2020). Quickservice restaurants are then gaining acceptance in Rivers State due to the ethnic diversity of different meal preparations (Habib et al., 2011), and they are being visited on a daily basis. Following this development and the high profits that are generated by quick service restaurants, the industry has recorded intense competition within the past few years (Haghighi, Dorosti, Rahnama & Hoseinpour, 2012).

Empirical Review

Zha and Melewa (2024) examined the impact of sensory brand experience (i.e. visual, auditory, olfactory, tactile, and taste) influencing sensory brand experience leading to brand loyalty through customer satisfaction, brand attachment, and customer lovemarks. It also investigated the role of employee empathy in moderating the effect of sensory brand experience on customer satisfaction, brand attachment, and customer lovemarks. The results suggest that five sensory cues have a significant impact on sensory brand experience and, in turn, contribute to customer satisfaction, brand attachment, and customer lovemarks. Krupka (2023) explored the influence of sensory marketing on brand perception. The research was conducted on a sample of 189 respondents from the Republic of Croatia. To test the hypotheses factor and regression analyses were used. The main findings of this research are: a) involvement of multiple senses in the consumer-brand relationship has a positive effect on brand perception; b) the greater the frequency of involving multiple senses in the consumer-brand relationship, the more positive effect it has on brand perception; and c) the higher intensity of sensory involvement in the consumer-brand relationship does not have a significant effect on brand perception.

Sayed (2023) examined the impact of sensory marketing on managing a sustainable fast-food business in Egypt. The study explored the influence of using the five sensory marketing factors, customer perceptions, satisfaction, and repurchase or revisit intention. Online surveys were used to collect data. A sample of 176 participants who visited fast food restaurants in Greater Cairo was received. The statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 23. According to the findings of the study, restaurant customers place a higher value on multisensory experiences, which influences their perceptions, satisfaction, and repurchase intentions. Gupta and Misha (2020) aimed to understand better the influence of sensory marketing on consumer by enhancing promotional effectiveness. The study was conducted through survey using structured questionnaire and analysis will be done using SPSS 26. Questionnaire was collected through convenient sampling. This study found that customers are a key factor for building successful brands because the brand image is constructed in their minds and imagination.

Sensory model can help companies to create multi-sensory brand- experiences and practical guidance and contemporary examples for implementing sensory marketing strategies offer a base for building the perfect brand experiences.

Dissabandara (2020) analyzed the influence of sensory marketing strategies on brand loyalty and the mediating effect of brand love: with special reference to franchised fast food chains in sri lanka. A quantitative research strategy was opted and stratified random sampling method was used to collect the data from 500 respondents as initially planned. Finally, 379 questionnaires were used for the final analysis after the initial data screening process. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used by the researcher to test the hypotheses whilst descriptive statistical methods were also used. AMOS-23 software was used for the statistical analysis. Results proved that sensory marketing strategies significantly influence brand loyalty behavior whilst brand love impacts on brand loyalty as verified in empirical evidences. Woo-Hyuk, Sang-Ho and Kyung-Sook (2020) examined effects of sensory marketing on customer satisfaction and revisit intention in the hotel industry. Data were collected from customers in hotels in South Korea, after which 286 usable surveys were processed. To investigate the data, we used descrip- tive statistics, confirmatory factor analysis, and structural equation modelling. The results reveal that there is a positive relationship between sensory marketing by hotels and customer satisfaction and that customer satisfaction significantly influenced revisit intentions. The present study puts forward the following hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between auditory perception and customer satisfaction of quick-service restaurants in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand trust of quick-service restaurants in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty of quick-service restaurants in Rivers State.

Methodology

This study adopts a cross-sectional research design with a correlational investigation type. The population of this study comprised the 15 registered quick-service restaurants operating in Rivers State which are also enlisted in the Nigerian Directories and Search Engine. The study adopts the Census method and administered four (4) copies of questionnaire to management staff from each of the 15 firms, making it a total of 60 respondents for the study. These managers included Operations Managers, Customer Service Managers, Marketing Managers and Supervisors of quick service restaurants in Rivers State. With the help of Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) is used to test the hypotheses and figure out the relationship between green sourcing and economic sustainability.

Table 1: Reliability Test - Cronbach's Alpha Analysis

S/N	Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach's Coefficients	Alpha
1	Auditory Perception	3	0.911	
2	Brand Satisfaction	3	0.893	
3	Brand Trust	3	0.963	
4	Brand Loyalty	3	0.964	

Source: SPSS Output form field data

As shown in Table 1, the results of the Cronbach’s alpha analysis revealed that all the variables in the study produced high Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients indicating that, there is inter-item consistency among the variables in the study. This means that, if this study is conducted again in similar condition, the results would be similar to the results of our study.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Audition

	N	Minimu m	Maximu m	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
To what extent does your organization use sound elements, such with the brand’s identity? as jingles or music, to55 create memorable brand experiences?	55	1	5	229	4.16	1.135	1.288
To what extent does your organization ensure that audio cues in advertisements align To what extent does your organization leverage auditory elements to evoke specific emotions in customers? To what extent does your organization use sound to enhance the customer experience in55 physical or online stores?	55	1	5	227	4.13	1.001	1.002
	55	1	5	230	4.18	1.073	1.152
Valid N (listwise)	55						

Source: Researcher’s Desk, 2024.

Table 2 depicts high mean scores of the questionnaire items ranging over 3.00, this means that greater number of the respondents expressed very high and high extents acceptance to the research question with respect to audition. However, it can be seen that questions 4 and 5 which sought to determine the extent to which Quick Service Restaurants in Rivers State leverage auditory elements to evoke specific emotions in customers, and use sound to enhance the customer experience in physical or online stores, have the highest mean score of 4.18 respectively. This shows that questions 3 and 4 have the strongest influence on the variables.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Brand Satisfaction

N	Minimu m	Maximu m	Sum	Mean	n	Variance

To what extent do you believe that your customers are satisfied with the overall quality of your brand's offerings?	55	1	5	232	4.22	1.272	1.618
To what extent do you believe that your brand meets the expectations of its customers?	55	1	5	232	4.22	1.197	1.433
To what extent do you believe that your brand provides value for money to its customers?	55	1	5	230	4.18	1.188	1.411
To what extent do you believe that your brand delivers consistent satisfaction across different customer interactions?	55	1	5	234	4.25	1.190	1.415
Valid N (listwise)	55						

Source: Researcher's Desk, 2024.

Table 3 depicts high mean scores of the questionnaire items ranging over 3.00, this means that greater number of the respondents expressed very high and high extents acceptance to the research question with respect to brand satisfaction. However, it can be seen that question 4 which sought to determine the extent to which Quick Service Restaurants in Rivers State brands deliver consistent satisfaction across different customer interactions, has the highest mean score of 4.25. This shows that question 4 has the strongest influence on the variables.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Brand Trust

Std.	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Deviation	Variance	
To what extent do you believe that your customers trust the claims made by your brand in advertisements?	55	1	5	222	4.04	.860	.739
To what extent do you believe that your							

customers perceive your brand as reliable? To what extent do you believe that your brand consistently delivers on its promises?	55	1	5	220	4.00	.882	.778
To what extent do you believe that your customers consider your brand to be transparent in its operations?	55	1	5	229	4.16	1.214	1.473
Valid N (listwise)	55			240	4.36	1.060	1.125

Source: Researcher’s Desk, 2024

Table 4 depicts high mean scores of the questionnaire items ranging over 3.00, this means that greater number of the respondents expressed very high and high extents acceptance to the research question with respect to brand trust. However, it can be seen that question 4 which sought to determine the extent to Quick Service Restaurants in Rivers State consider their brand to be transparent in its operations, has the highest mean score of 4.46. This shows that question 4 has the strongest influence on the variables.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Brand Loyalty

	<u>N</u>	<u>Minimu</u> <u>m</u>	<u>Maximu</u> <u>m</u>	<u>Sum</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>Deviatio</u> <u>n</u>	<u>Variance</u>
To what extent do you believe that your customers prefer your brand over competitors?		1	5	224	4.07	1.245	1.550
To what extent do you believe that your customers consistently purchase products or services from your brand?		1	5	231	4.20	.779	.607
To what extent do you believe that your							

customers are emotionally attached to your brand?	1	5	223	4.05	.848	.719	Std.
To what extent do you believe that your customers actively advocate for your brand to others?	1	5	233	4.24	1.122	1.258	55
Valid N (listwise)	55						55

Source: Researcher’s Desk, 2024.

Table 5 depicts high mean scores of the questionnaire items ranging over 3.00, this means that greater number of the respondents expressed very high and high extents acceptance to the research question with respect to brand loyalty. However, it can be seen that question 4 which sought to determine the extent to Quick Service Restaurants in Rivers State that customers actively advocate for their brand over others, has the highest mean score of 4.24. This shows that question 4 has the strongest influence on the variables. **Bivariate Analysis**

The secondary data analysis was carried out through the use of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) tool at a 95% confidence level. Specifically, the tests cover hypotheses H_{01} to H_{03} . We have depended on the Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation tool to carry out the analysis thus the probability criterion of 0.05 significance level was adopted for accepting the null hypotheses at ($P > 0.05$) or rejecting the hypotheses at ($P < 0.05$).

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand satisfaction of quick service restaurants in Rivers State.

Table 6: Relationship between Auditory Perception and Brand Satisfaction

Auditory Perception	Brand Satisfaction
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Auditory Perception	Pearson Correlation	1	.758**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
N	55	55	
Brand Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.758**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
N	55	55	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2024.

From the SPSS output on Table 6, it can be observed that there is a correlation coefficient of 0.758** between auditory perception and brand satisfaction, indicating a strong and positive relationship between auditory perception and brand satisfaction, More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand satisfaction. This further implies that most of the changes in brand satisfaction among quick service restaurants in Rivers State are caused by auditory perception while others are caused by externalities. Based on this, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand satisfaction of quick service restaurants in Rivers State and accept the alternate that there is strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand satisfaction of quick service restaurants in Rivers State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand trust of quick service restaurants in Rivers State.

Table 7: Relationship between Auditory Perception and Brand Trust

		Auditory Perception	Brand Trust
Auditory Perception	Pearson Correlation	1	.757**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
N	55	55	
Brand Trust	Pearson Correlation	.757**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
N	55	55	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2024.

From the SPSS output on Table 7, it can be observed that there is a correlation coefficient of 0.757** between auditory perception and brand trust, indicating a strong and positive relationship between auditory perception and brand trust, More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand trust. This further implies that most of the changes in brand trust among quick service restaurants in Rivers State are caused by auditory perception while others are caused by externalities. Based on this, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand trust of quick service restaurants in Rivers State and accept the alternate that there is strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand trust of quick service restaurants in Rivers State.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty of quick service restaurants in Rivers State.

Table 8: Relationship between Auditory Perception and Brand Loyalty

		Auditory Perception		Brand Loyalty
Auditory Perception	Pearson Correlation	1	.788**	
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
N	55	55		
Brand Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	.788**	1	
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
N	55		55	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2024.

From the SPSS output on Table 8, it can be observed that there is a correlation coefficient of 0.788** between auditory perception and brand loyalty, indicating a strong and positive relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty. More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty. This further implies that most of the changes in brand loyalty among quick service restaurants in Rivers State are caused by auditory perception while others are caused by externalities. Based on this, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty of quick service restaurants in Rivers State and accept the alternate that there is strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty of quick service restaurants in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of the study revealed a correlation coefficient of 0.758** between auditory perception and brand satisfaction, indicating a strong and positive relationship between auditory perception and brand satisfaction, More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand satisfaction. The analysis of the study also revealed a correlation coefficient of 0.757** between auditory perception and brand trust, indicating a strong and positive relationship between auditory perception and brand trust, More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand trust. The study analysis results showed a correlation coefficient of 0.788** between auditory perception and brand loyalty, indicating a strong and positive relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty. More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a strong significant relationship between auditory perception and brand loyalty.

These findings are validated by the empirical findings of Zha and Melewa (2024) as they examined the impact of sensory brand experience (i.e. visual, auditory, olfactory, tactile, and taste) influencing sensory brand experience leading to brand loyalty through customer satisfaction, brand attachment, and customer lovemarks. The results suggest that five sensory cues have a significant impact on sensory brand experience and, in turn, contribute to customer satisfaction, brand attachment, and customer love marks. In line with the findings of this study, Krupka (2023) explored the influence of sensory marketing on brand perception and found that a) involvement of multiple senses in the consumer-brand relationship has a positive effect on brand perception; b) the greater the frequency of involving multiple senses in the consumerbrand relationship, the more positive effect it has on brand perception; and c) the higher intensity of sensory involvement in the consumer-brand relationship does not have a significant effect on brand perception.

The result of the findings is in line with the findings of Sayed (2023) which explored the impact of sensory marketing on managing a sustainable fast-food business in Egypt and revealed that the senses of sight, smell, and touch have a positive significant impact on customer satisfaction in fast-food restaurants. Kuma and Kumar (2020) investigated the role of sensory marketing on consumer behaviour and its influence on brand equity in e-commerce platforms and indicated that multi-sensory marketing technique plays a significant role in influencing consumer behaviour and has a palpable effect on brand equity. Gupta and Misha (2020) aimed to understand better the influence of sensory marketing on consumer by enhancing promotional effectiveness. The study revealed that sensory model can help companies to create multisensory brand- experiences. Dissabandara (2020) proved that sensory marketing strategies significantly influence brand loyalty behavior whilst brand love impacts on brand loyalty as verified in empirical evidences.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, and to the extent of its consistency with results of similar previous studies, we conclude that auditory perception has significant nexus with brand performance of quick service restaurants in Rivers State. Thus, pleasant auditory environments can encourage consumers to feel more comfortable, which may lead to increased spending by the customer and more profit to the organization. Background music or ambient sounds can affect consumer behavior, including the amount of time they spend in-store and their overall shopping experience.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study and given its consistency with the result of similar studies, we put forward the following recommendations:

1. Managers of quick service restaurants should carefully curate their auditory landscapes to enable an atmosphere that appeals to their target audience and align their services with their brand performance.
- 2 Managers of quick service restaurants should also consider the strategic role of auditory perception in their quest to understand consumer behaviour, this would boost brand loyalty as well as improve overall performance.

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